

A Geographical Analysis of Socio-economic Level of Sample Village - Newari of Masturi Block Bilaspur Plain - Chhattisgarh State

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Abstract: Development literally means a new situation that emerges. Development achieved through planned efforts is termed as planned development. If the growth is natural it is known as natural development. Development however is a two dimensional phenomenon, depicting a positive aspect in a given context on the one hand and negative aspect on the other. When it proceeds towards positive direction it becomes development, so it is obvious that gaining a better level of living is the normative phenomenon of desirable change. The present paper is based on primary and secondary data to find out the socio-economic level and assess the living standard of rural population of in this area.

Key words: - Development, dimensional, phenomenon, normative.

Introduction:-

The Bilaspur district is situated in the north western part of Chhattisgarh state. Physically it's called Bilaspur plain', a part of Chhattisgarh Basin. It extends from 21.47° N to 23.8° north latitude and 81.14° E to 83.15° E longitude, covering an area of 6375 sq Kms. Masturi block is situated in south eastern part of bilaspur district and physically it comes under bilaspur plain area. Masturi block occupies a total of 737 sq km geographical area. This block is bounded by three rivers Arpa, Lilagar and Seonoth flows the western and southern Port boundaries. There are 171 villages and 105 Gram Panchayat. Newari village is selected at random sampling for our research studies.

Study Area:-

Newari sample village is situated in the southern part of Masturi block in Bilaspur district. It comes under Patwari Halka number 43. It extends from 21°52'30" N to 21°54'00" North latitude and 82°16'25" E to 82°18'10" East longitude. The total geographical area of the village Newari is 308.30 hectare. In Newari village there are 130 household according to census 2001 and total population is 517 persons. The 102 house and field surveyed during field year 2009. The present studies make focus on the physical, social, cultural and economic activities assessment for the socio-economic development of this area.

Objectives:-

In the study area, the following objectives have been stated :-

- 1) To examine the geographical account of the human resources of the study area and finding out where, how and in what way we can bring phenomenal changes in this surveyed village.
- 2) To analyse the socio-economic condition of the village and assess the infrastructure facilities for the development of study area.

Hypothesis:-

Most of the rural population is involved in non-agricultural works.

Data – Base and Methodology:-

The present study is primarily based on the field survey, conducted in which scheduled, Question and interview by door to door survey secondary data have been collected from various publish government records and census reports. The district census hand book also has been consulted for data analysis. General statistics and methods are used for conclude phenomena of village Newari.

Result and discussion :-

Before the analyzing the block and village Newari, the pattern of socio-economic development in the study area. We have discussed population structure, age sex ratio, age group composition, economic activity and cultural element. It consist demographic characteristics, which is the one of main components of social development. It is highly determine by level of development of any particular area. According to 2011 census the total population of Masturi block is 199377 person population density is 269 person per 5 Kgm. Decided growth of population of Masturi block in 2001 year is 2.1% The land is mostly appropriate for agriculture. This area occupied night density population. The sex ratio of Masturi block is 989 and the literary rate is 50.2%. In 2011 census The total population of Masturi block is 217425 In sample village Newari also studies details for research work as a case study. of geographical point of view. The village comes also under phi ally plain area. The total population of village Newari is in 2011 census is 582 persons. The village Newari comes under the Patwari Hlaka No. 43 of Masturi block in Bilaspur district. It extended 21°52'30" N to 21°54' N latitude and 82°16' E to 82°18' East longitude. The total geographical area of this viallge is 308.30 hector and number of house hold are 130.

Table No. 01, Village Newari – Population Census 1981 to 2011

1981			1991			2001			2011		
M	F	Total									
290	278	568	282	275	557	310	207	517	302	280	582

Table No. 02, Village Newari – Cost Wise Population Structure – Census 1981-2011

Year	General			Scheduled Cost			Scheduled Tribe		
	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F
1981	341	180	161	76	34	42	151	76	75
1991	308	152	156	100	53	47	149	77	72
2001	488	250	238	63	35	28	166	133	33
2011	582	310	272	79	39	40	179	140	39

Sources: Census of India Bilaspur District (C.G.)

During field survey (In 2014) about 93 families are survey through door to door and found Total population 628 person which is 329 male and 299 is female population and caste wise population found total 309 general categories and total 156 are S.T. Population and total 87 are

SC population and total 76 are OBC population. From a sample survey we get trust the scheduled cast population is very low to Newari. Have is ST population with more than other categories. The sex ratio of sample Newari vilage is 908 females per thousand males.

Table No. 03, Village Newari : Distribution of Population

Age Group Wise

Age Group	Male	Female
0-5	49	20
5-10	34	29
10-15	38	33
15-20	25	23
20-25	29	40
25-30	32	35
30-35	28	32
35-40	27	20
40-45	12	16
45-50	14	14
50-55	13	10
55-60	20	18
above- 60	18	13

Sources : Surveyed Dated

From above table the high person format age group 15 to 40 in rule male and female both low age persons in above age group 60.

95, similarly in 2001 census total literacy 283 which is male 157 and female 126. According to 2011 census the total literacy 352 which is male 210 and female 142. From the sample so my we get 628 person total population which is (329 male and 299 female) the literacy is 337 person total which is 198 is male literacy and 139 is female.

Literacy :-

The literacy rate tabulated both date primary and secondary. According to census village Newari in 1981 the total literacy is 164 person which is male 115 and female 49 and in 1991 census year total literacy 295 which is male 200 and female

Table No. 04, Village Newari – Literacy

1981			1991			2001			2011		
Total	M	F	Total	M	F	Total	M	F	Total	M	F
164	115	49	295	200	95	283	157	126	352	210	142

Sources: Census of India, Bilaspur District (C.G.)

Table No. 05, Village Newari – Literacy Rate In Surveyed Family

Total Population	Literacy Population			Illiterate Population		
523 (93 Family)	Total	M	F	Total	M	F
	337	194	143	186	82	104

Sources: Surveyed Date - 2014

Occupation Structure:-

According to 2001 census the number of total workers is 194 persons where male is 131

persons and female is 63 person The main working Population in 190 which is 128 male person and 62 female persons. Given below table

Table No. : 06, Village Newari: Occupational Structure

Year	Main Workers					Marginal Workers	Non Workers
	Cultivator	Agricultural Labour	Household Industries	Other Workers	Total		
1981	73	158	01	07	239	05	324
1991	98	160	01	06	265	01	398
2001	67	108	03	12	190	04	323
2011	102	118	05	15	240	06	338

Sources : Census Data

Table No. 07, Village Newari – Occupational Structure Surveyed Family

Total	Cultivator	Agriculture Labour	Service	Yavsay	Other	Non-worker
542	97	124	15	12	12	282

Sources : Surveyed Date - 2014

In sample survey, the total worker populations is 350, where male is 184 person and female is 166 person. The total non-worker is 282 persons whose male is 146 and female is 136 persons - The total main workers found in surveyed village in 2014 is 350, in which is cultivator is 187,

Agriculture is 187, Agriculture Labour is 124, other services participator is 39 person in village Newari.

Land Use:- Land use of Newari village given following table no. 08 -

Table No. 08, Village Newari – Land Use

Land Use	Area (In hectare)	% of Total Area
Forest	16.703	5.41
Fallow Land	12.509	4.07
Cultivable Land	14.396	4.66
Non Available for Cultivation	12.587	4.08
Land put on other uses	12.463	9.52
Net Sown Area	232.706	75.48
Total Area	308.301	100.00

Sources : Land Record Office, Bilaspur (C.G.)

Size Of Land Holding :-

Table No. : 09, Village Newari : Size of Land Holding in Surveyed Families

Caste	Area of Land Holding Size							Total No. of Family
	0 – 2	2 -4	4 – 6	6 – 8	8 - 10	10 – 12	Above 12	
GENERAL	13	8	3	4	4	3	1	36
OBC	6	-	-	-	2	-	-	08
SC	6	1	-	-	-	-	-	07
ST	6	2	1	-	-	-	-	09
TOTAL	10	10	4	4	6	3	1	60

Sources : Surveyed Data 2014

In our surveyed family most of the family comes under small farmers. 31 family have 0-2 acre land holding, 24 acre land Village Land holding

family are 10, in General Cast family are total 13, size of 0-2 acre land size.

Table No. - 15 , Village Newari : Total Land Holding in Surveyed Family

Land Holding Size	Surveyed Family	Total (Area) Land Holding
0 – 2	31	35.8
2 – 4	10	32.1
4 – 6	04	22.2
6 – 8	04	29.3
8 – 10	06	60.2
10 - 12	03	36.1
Above 12	01	32.0
Total	59	248.7

Sources : Surveyed Data 2014

Irrigation :- In the Newari village the irrigated land in 76.50%, and non irrigated land of this village 23.50%.

Table No. – 01, Village Newari : Irrigated Land

Total Agricultural Land (Area)	Irrigated Land (Hectare)	Non-irrigated Land (Hectare)
269.63	206.283	63.3

Sources : Land Record Office, Bilaspur (C.G.)

Agriculture Pattern :-

Agriculture is the main base of economy of Newari. The primitive method of agriculture are found in this village some family are uses new methods and technology in ours fields. Most of agriculture land are small. The total Net sown

area of the village 232-706 hector. Rabi, Kharif and Rabi two types of crop curveted in 249.931 hectare. Paddy and Tiwra are mostly production in area are respectively 213 · 193 acres and 21.317 acres.

Table No. - 12 , Village Newari : Agriculture Pattern

Crop	Area (In Acre)	%
Paddy	213.193	85.30
Wheat	4.047	1.63
Tiwra	21.317	8.52
Other	11.374	4.53
Total	249.931	100.00

Sources : Agriculture Statistical and Department, Bilaspur

Live Stock :- The villages have large number of livestock animal as well as these are domestic animals uses also agricultural and also used in agriculture fields.

Table No. – 13, Village Newari : Amount of Live Stock

Live Stock	Numbers
Cow	81
Ox	13
Bullock	20
Dog	04
Calf	33

Sources : Surveyed Data

Agricultural Equipments :-

Traditional method of agriculture are used in the agriculture field in many family but some farmer who have big size land holding they have used modern technology like machine tractor, fan,

wishmuld seeds pa and other techniques. Generally plough and cart is the main agricultural equipments but in this Village 5 tractors and 7 winning fan use tube well for irrigation are founds during surveying.

Table No. – 13, Village Newari : Agriculture Equipment

Agriculture Equipment	Number	Used No. of Family
Bullock Cart	2	15
Ox Plough	12	35
Tractor	5	5
Thresher	3	5
Winning Fan	7	10

Income Level :- Agriculture is the main sources of income of the villagers in Mewari In surveyed family most of the family are come to the category are below 15000.

Table No. – 14, Village Newari : Income Level

Income Group in Rs.	Caste				Total Family
	Gen.	OBC	SC	ST	
0 – 15000	17	04	04	14	39
15000 – 25000	10	06	07	08	31
25000 – 35000	02	01	01	01	05
35000 – Above	19	01	02	04	26

Conclusion :-

From the above investigation, analysis and interpretation, it can be concluded that village Mewari is semi developed area, most of the people work as cultivators in their agricultural land. The main crop is paddy and another crop is tiwra, wheat. Few farmers are using HYV seeds got agricultural land is irrigated according to field surveyed report. The study also reveals that the socio-economic development of the study area is not found to be at a satisfactory level. The people depend on some other region or sources for their fundamental necessities. Though a lot of schemes and programs have been incorporated for the development of the blocks and various constitution and administrative facilities have also been provided to people, only some people have been benefited from these schemes and programs. The ratio is not up to the mark or satisfactory for their socio-economic conditions.

References :-

1. Alvi, zamir, 2005, statistical Geography methods and application, Rawat publication, Jalpur Pp 61-75.
2. Berry, B.J.L., 1960, An Inductive Approach to regionalization of Economic Development, in Ginsberg, N. (ed) Essays on geography and economic development Chicago.
3. Das gupta, 1971, socio economic classification of district: A statistical approach, economic and political weekly, Aug. 14, P – 145.
4. Goswami, C, 2002, "Agriculture and use in the plains of Assam", Economic and political weekly Vol. 37, no 49 Pp 94891 - 4893.
5. Hussain, Majid, 2007, systematic Agricultural Geography, Rawat publication , Jalpur.
6. Kothari, S. 1999 Agricultural land use and population - A Geographical Analysis, Shiva, publisher and distributor, Udaipur, - PP. 30-52.
7. Lambin, Rounsevell and Geist, 2002 " A Agriculture Land use model able to predict changes in land use! intensity". Agriculture Eco systems and Environment, vol. 82, PP 321-331.
8. Richter, 1984, "Land use and Land Transformation ! Geo-Journal vol-8. No.1 pp 67-74.
9. Shanani, L., 1987, "The impact of irrigation" Land Transformation", Geo Journal, vol. 8, No. 1. PP-67-74.
10. 1934, "Land Utilization survey of Britain" Geographical Review. Vol. 24, No. 4, PP 646-650.